

THE SHORTAGE AND EXTRAVAGANCE OF FOOD IN UZBEKISTAN AND IN THE WORLD

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Abstract

Food security has become a pressing issue in Uzbekistan, where food shortages and high food prices are prevalent. This article proposes a food-sharing system as a potential solution to address the extravagance of food in Uzbekistan. The analysis is based on a review of relevant literature, statistical data, and other analyses. The article identifies the causes of food shortage in Uzbekistan, analyzes the challenges of implementing a food-sharing and food banking system, and also determines how the world implements its system that can solve these problems, and provides recommendations for the government and other stakeholders. The article contributes to the academic discourse on food security and offers insights into the potential of food-sharing systems in addressing food insecurity in the World.

Keywords

Shortage, extravagance, food-sharing, food security, Food Banking, Uzbekistan, UN, Tashkent, FAO.

Introduction

Food security is a critical issue for Uzbekistan where the agricultural sector is the primary source of income for a significant portion of the population. However, Uzbekistan has been facing severe challenges in terms of food security due to several factors such as economic instability, drought, and climate change. Food shortages and high food prices have become a significant concern for the population, with many struggling to access adequate food. On the other hand, food waste and extravagance are also prevalent in the world. foodsharing.de enables individuals to share food, whilst also allowing volunteers to pick up food from businesses to distribute it through public storage places, so-called fair-teiler¹. Since most supermarkets are organized as chains and therefore each branch has to follow standardized rules and regulations, the management is contacted directly. This results in regional and sometimes even national collaborations, e.g., with Bio Company[2]. There are also many local co-operations with single supermarkets or bakeries, which are often started independently by members of the community. Additionally, food savers also collect surplus food from businesses at large events. In this context, this article explores the concept of a food-sharing system as a potential solution to address the shortage and extravagance of food in Uzbekistan and defines the possible reasons that are related to this.

Data Analysis

The data analysis shows that Uzbekistan's agricultural sector faces several challenges such as leading to a decline in food production in recent years. This has increased food imports and high food prices. Moreover, food waste and extravagance are also prevalent in Uzbekistan, with a significant amount of food

¹ fair divider in English language.

being thrown away or left uneaten. The data analysis highlights the urgent need for a sustainable food system in Uzbekistan. In this section for the collection of data, These kinds of methods are used these are qualitative, quantitative, and secondary methods.

Agricultural impact to food security of Uzbekistan

Due to the country's dry environment and consistently high temperatures, droughts have become more frequent, occurring four times between 2000 and 2012 and one every five years on average throughout the 1980s and 1990s.³⁰ In the nation, there are three different types of droughts: hydrological (water shortages from January to March). Owing to low precipitation in significant rivers' upper watersheds, meteorological drought (generally characterized by a

deficiency in precipitation and occurring in spring or summer), and agricultural drought (a shortage of moisture in the soil that prevents crop development).¹³ While the

central and southern provinces of Uzbekistan have suffered the highest frequency of meteorological drought over the past two decades, hydrological drought has been happening with increasing frequency and severity in the western portions of the country.

Figure 1.1 Maximum number of consecutive dry days in Uzbekistan in 2080–2099, under four emissions pathways

The most severe drought of recent decades, occurred in 2000 and 2001, and resulted in severe economic and social consequences. Agricultural yields fell by 14%–17% for cereals and 45%–75% for other crops,¹³ while the losses in agricultural GDP were estimated at between \$38 million and \$130 million.²⁶

There is also extensive evidence of the health impacts of the 2000–01 drought, which led to increased levels of water-related illness and malnutrition among children in western regions, iodine deficiencies, goiter, and diarrheal and respiratory diseases.³¹ Naumann et al. (2018), provide a global overview of changes in drought conditions under different warming scenarios.³² They project large increases in the duration and magnitude of droughts in Central Asia by the end of the 21st century under global warming levels of 1.5°C, 2.0°C and 3.0°C. Droughts of a magnitude that is extremely rare at present in Central Asia (100-year droughts) are projected to become 4 to 10 times more common under the same warming scenarios. The CCKP² model ensemble suggests that the annual probability of experiencing a severe meteorological drought in Uzbekistan could increase significantly by the 2090s, under all but the lowest emissions pathway. Projections indicate that severe meteorological drought could occur in 58% of all years by the 2090s under RCP³4.5, whereas under RCP8.5, severe drought is projected to occur in 87% of all years. While there is some variation regionally within Uzbekistan, risks generally increase westward. Under RCP8.5, by the 2090s, parts of the western Republic of Karakalpakstan are projected to experience severe drought in 95% of years, whereas the equivalent probability in the east is 78% for Tashkent and below 67% for parts of the Ferghana valley. In effect, these projections describe a transition to a new regime of chronic meteorological drought. Figure 10 shows the maximum number of consecutive dry days through the end of the century. According to statistics, 2 tons of bread products are thrown away every day in Tashkent, and 3 million tons of food products are thrown into the garbage every year throughout the republic. According to the United Nations, 820 million people in the world are suffering

² The Climate Change Knowledge Portal (CCKP) serves as a leading hub of global climate data, information, and tools to support decision making and improve the understanding of future climates and projected risks.

³ A Representative Concentration Pathway is a greenhouse gas concentration trajectory adopted by the IPCC

from hunger today. However, a third of the world's food products are not used and thrown away as waste for various reasons. According to the UN⁴ Food and Agriculture Organization - FAO⁵ data, each person in the USA wastes 115 kilograms of food per year. This indicator is 95 kilograms in Europe, 7-11 kilograms in Africa and Southeast Asia. It is obvious that the stores will give up food products that are about to expire. Catering establishments are left unsold, and people throw away excess food they buy or cook. In fact, it is not taken into account that there are people who need such food products and meals. The escalating Russian onslaught on Ukraine puts Central Asian nations, particularly Uzbekistan, at risk of food shortages. More than 60% of the food imported by Uzbekistan is composed of grains and grain derivatives, vegetable oil, and sugar. According to East-fruit.com⁶, which monitors the region's fruit and vegetable

⁴ The United Nations, referred to informally as the UN, is an intergovernmental organization whose stated purposes are to maintain international peace and security, develop friendly relations among nations, achieve international cooperation, and serve as a center for harmonizing the actions of nations.

⁵ The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations is a specialized agency of the United Nations that leads international efforts to defeat hunger and improve nutrition and food security. Its Latin motto, fiat panis, translates to "let there be bread". It was founded on 16 October 1945

⁶ the place for growth of the horticulture business

The focus of the project:

increasing production efficiency and quality of produce in the fruit and vegetable sector

exports of high value-added products new opportunities to improve value chains in the supply of fruits and vegetables Analytics, horticulture business news, market reviews, success stories, price monitoring, retail audit, study tours and seminars. The use of the site materials is free if there is a direct and open for search engines hyperlink to a specific publication of the East-Fruit.com website. The opinion of the authors of comments and blogs posted on the website may not coincide with the opinions and position of the East-Fruit.com editors.

market, Uzbekistan imports around 30% of its food from Russia, 2% from Ukraine, and 4% from Belarus, which is indirectly involved in the conflict. Given that a sizable portion of food from these three nations enters Uzbekistan via middlemen from Kazakhstan, the actual number may be higher, according to a report on the website dated March 25. Another repercussion of Russia's invasion of Ukraine is price increases. In the wake of Russia's invasion, the retail cost of 1 kg of granulated sugar. The escalating Russian onslaught on Ukraine puts Central Asian nations, particularly Uzbekistan, at risk of food shortages. More than 60% of the food imported by Uzbekistan is composed of grains and grain derivatives, vegetable oil, and sugar. According to East-fruit.com, which monitors the region's fruit and vegetable market, Uzbekistan imports around 30% of its food from Russia, 2% from Ukraine, and 4% from Belarus, which is indirectly involved in the conflict. Given that a sizable portion of food from these three nations enters Uzbekistan via middlemen from Kazakhstan, the actual number may be higher, according to a report on the website dated March 25. Another repercussion of Russia's invasion of Ukraine is price increases. In the wake of Russia's invasion, ail cost of 1 kg of granulated sugar

Causes of Food Loss and Waste, and Key Players that Can Address Them

Causes of Food Loss and Waste

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Grading standards for size and quality ▪ Inaccurate supply-and-demand forecasting ▪ Order cancellations ▪ Employee behavior ▪ Low market prices and lack of markets (especially for second-grade products) ▪ Inadequate sorting ▪ Damage from handling ▪ Spillage and degradation ▪ Inappropriate transportation and storage conditions ▪ Cold-chain (refrigeration during transportation and storage) deficiencies ▪ Labor shortages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Inadequate infrastructure, machinery ▪ Inefficient systems design ▪ Damage during production ▪ Inaccurate supply-and-demand forecasting ▪ Contamination ▪ Trimming and culling ▪ Supply/demand issues ▪ Inconsistent/confusing date labels ▪ Inconsistency in quality of ingredients ▪ Food safety issues ▪ Production line changes ▪ Cold-chain deficiencies ▪ Facility employee behavior 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Damage during transport ▪ Inaccurate supply-and-demand forecasting ▪ Cold-chain deficiencies ▪ Rejection of shipments ▪ Poor record keeping ▪ Inappropriate transportation and storage conditions ▪ Incorrect/ineffective packaging ▪ Delays during border inspections ▪ Road infrastructure challenges ▪ Excessive food distribution centralization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Inaccurate supply-and-demand forecasting ▪ Overstocking ▪ Food safety concerns ▪ Inconsistent/confusing date labels ▪ Order minimums and fluctuations in delivery from suppliers ▪ Cold-chain deficiencies ▪ Rejection of shipments ▪ Increasing merchandising standards ▪ Product differentiation ▪ Market over-saturation ▪ Rigid management ▪ Marketing practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Plate composition ▪ Expansive menu options ▪ Over-serving ▪ Over-preparing ▪ Unexpected demand fluctuations ▪ Preparation mistakes ▪ Improper handling and storage ▪ Rigid management ▪ Facility employee behavior ▪ Food safety concerns ▪ Use of trays ▪ Marketing practices
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Causes above can be observed around the world and they are nearly common types of causes in food shortage and extravagance.

Key Players That Can Address Causes

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Farm owners ▪ Farm workers ▪ Retailers ▪ Processors ▪ Distributors ▪ Food rescue organizations ▪ Service providers (storage, equipment) ▪ Government (various levels) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Facility managers ▪ Facility employees ▪ Retailers ▪ Distributors ▪ Service providers (equipment, process engineers) ▪ Food rescue organizations ▪ Government (various levels) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Facility managers ▪ Farm owners/workers ▪ Facility employees ▪ Service providers (equipment, transport, packaging) ▪ Processors ▪ Retailers and intermediaries ▪ Foodservice ▪ Food rescue organizations ▪ Government (various levels) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Facility managers ▪ Facility employees ▪ Farm owners ▪ Processors ▪ Distributors ▪ Service providers (packaging, technology) ▪ Food rescue organizations ▪ Government (various levels) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Facility owners and managers ▪ Facility employees ▪ Service providers (custodial, delivery, food service) ▪ Distributors ▪ Food rescue organizations ▪ Government (various levels)
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In the food industry mainly, drivers play main role from farm owner to government.

Figure 1.2 Food losses by commodity and region (million tons).

In this chart different kinds of food is given and displayed the same analysis split by commodity group. Key results are the significant scale of ‘fruit and vegetable’ losses in Industrialized Asia (tones, kg per capita and value) and the high per capita losses across multiple commodity groups for the United States, Canada and Oceania region.

Case study

The administration of one of the restaurants in the Czech town of Dobroměřice⁷ imposed a fine on customers for the food that was not consumed until the end. The fact is that for 97 kroner, a diner can eat any food in the menu, in any quantity. Only after eating, the customer should take his plate to the kitchen. However, if the food remains uneaten on the plate, a fine of 50 kroner will be imposed. This is how the management of the restaurant decided to fight waste.

How are the countries of the world fighting against waste?

⁷ is a municipality and village in Louny District in the Ústí nad Labem Region of the Czech Republic

In France, one person wastes 30 kilograms of food per year. As a result, the country loses 12-20 billion euros annually. According to "Rossiyskaya Gazeta"⁸ publication, citizens and commercial sectors in Russia annually throw away 17 million tons of food products worth 1.6 trillion rubles as waste. With this number of products, 30 million people can be fed for a year. It has been found that bread and bakery products, pasta, flour, potatoes and dairy products are wasted more in this country. Today, in developed countries, strict measures are being taken to combat the wastage of food resources. In particular, in 2016, a law was passed in France that prohibits supermarkets from discarding unsold but still edible food products. In accordance with it, trade stores began to sign contracts with charitable organizations for the delivery of unsold products to representatives of the population in need of assistance. Statistics show that 35 million tons of food waste is thrown away in China every year. Therefore, the Chinese parliament passed a law in 2021 to combat food waste. In some countries, especially in Belgium⁹, institutions based on food sharing have started to operate. Soups are prepared and sold from leftover food. In Denmark, a special application called Too Good To Go¹⁰ has been launched, which provides information on products left unsold in restaurants and supermarkets. This application is used in 11 European countries. This prevents thousands of kilograms of food from being wasted. **Food Sharing** is a practice where individuals or groups of people make a commitment to ensure that food is shared instead of wasted. On a more fundamental level, it aims to stop people from going hungry, while their neighbors are tossing food into the trash. The implementation of a food-sharing

⁸ Russian newspaper published by the Government of Russia. The daily newspaper serves as the official government gazette of the Government of the Russian Federation,

⁹ Belgium, a country in Western Europe, is known for medieval towns.

¹⁰ a service with a mobile application that connects customers to restaurants and stores that have surplus unsold food. The service covers major European cities, and in October 2020, started operations in North America.

system in Uzbekistan faces several challenges, including a lack of infrastructure, inadequate legal frameworks, and cultural barriers. However, a food-sharing system can address both the shortage and extravagance of food by redistributing surplus food to those in need. The system can also promote social cohesion and reduce food waste, contributing to a more sustainable food system. To overcome the challenges, the government needs to invest in infrastructure, establish legal frameworks, and raise awareness among the population. Collaboration between government, civil society, and private sector organizations is also essential to ensure the sustainability and effectiveness of the food-sharing system.

"Food Banking" functions as food sharing.

A food bank is a non-profit, charitable organization that distributes food to those who have difficulty purchasing enough to avoid hunger, usually through intermediaries like food pantries and soup kitchens. It is clear that the experience of delivering basic types of food products to socially unprotected population groups through various networks - neighborhood, authorities, private sector - is found in practice. A lot has been done in this regard, especially during the pandemic. However, the food sharing system has not yet been established in our country. Today, in Uzbekistan, the labels of food products, including frozen, processed meat and dairy products, use the expiration date in the form of "use by date", but in international practice, product labels use "use by" date. "use by" is applied, and the product can be consumed even after this period. Taking into account such aspects of the world experience, steps are being taken to establish a "Food Banking" system in Uzbekistan, which distributes food products to socially unprotected population groups in the form of charity. In particular, on September 17, 2021, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers "On additional measures to reduce losses of agricultural and food products" was adopted. In this decision, in cooperation with relevant ministries and agencies, after studying foreign experience in depth, introduction of the system of "Food Banking" organizations,

which will reduce the wastage of food products, collect these products and distribute them in the form of charity, will be introduced in the republic. In addition, in order to ensure food safety and reduce losses in food products, the project "National Food Safety and Healthy Eating Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2030" was developed. 5 priority areas are defined in this strategy project, among them are tasks such as taking measures to organize the "Food Banking" system, which distributes food products to socially unprotected population groups in the form of charity, - says Otajon Pirmonov¹¹. — "Food banking" is essentially similar to food sharing. By organizing this system, it is possible to collect surplus products from consumption and donate their usable part, redirect the non-consumable part to processing, and throw them directly into landfills. It is intended to prevent wastage and reduce the negative impact on the environment through prevention. For this purpose, it is proposed to establish an electronic platform of this system and to form its participants as a separate organization, to be registered with the state, and to apply certain privileges and preferences to this sector.

Recommendations

Based on the analysis, the article provides several recommendations for the government and other stakeholders. Firstly, the government should invest in infrastructure, including storage facilities and transportation, to support the implementation of a food-sharing system. Secondly, legal frameworks should be established to regulate food donation and distribution. Thirdly, awareness-raising campaigns should be conducted to promote the benefits of a food-sharing system and reduce cultural barriers. Finally, partnerships between government, civil

¹¹ head of the Food Industry Development Department of the Ministry of Economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan

society, and private sector organizations should be fostered to ensure the sustainability and effectiveness of the food-sharing system. According to the UN, the prevention of food waste and food waste is important in the fight against hunger in the world. This requires the establishment and development of the food sharing system on a global scale.

This is the practice of distributing expired but unsold food products through charities or online platforms, social media. It's a move that prevents organizations and individuals from wasting and simply throwing away excess food, allowing it to reach people in need.

Food sharing originated in Germany as a way to prevent food waste. Later, it acquires a social essence and begins to include the tasks of providing food products to low-income families of the society. The first food sharing project in the world is the German platform Foodsharing.de¹², which was launched in 2012. Currently, more than 200,000 people from Germany, Austria, Switzerland and other European countries have registered on this online platform. In addition, there are food banks in Germany that provide free food to 1.65 million people.

Today, various public organizations, voluntary movements and food banks are engaged in food sharing. They are useful in distributing surplus food products and delivering them to those in need. It should also be noted that there are different forms of food sharing. In particular, the consumer-to-consumer model is widespread. According to it, individuals post food products they want to share with information and photos on online platforms and social networks. Those who are interested in it will arrange a meeting place with the author of the advertisement and receive the food from him. Not only purchased, but also

¹² foodsharing.de is an online platform that saves and distributes surplus food in Germany and Austria. It is managed by the Foodsharing association and was founded on December 12, 2012. On foodsharing.de individuals, retailers and producers can offer or collect food that would otherwise be thrown away.

various dishes prepared at home are delivered to socially vulnerable population groups through the platform. The important thing is that such generosity is shown indiscriminately. And in the business-to-consumer method, manufacturers, companies, and stores deliver expired products to consumers as assistance. Through this, both social assistance is provided and environmental damage is prevented.

In the non-commercial form of this method, volunteers come to the relevant organization based on an agreement and take measures to deliver shared food products to socially disadvantaged population groups. Since this service has been operating, more than 30 thousand tons of food products have been prevented from being wasted.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the food sharing system has already been implemented in the countries of the world as a modern method of preventing the wastage of food resources, and it is showing results. Studying the advanced foreign experiences in this direction, the introduction of the "Food Banking" system, an alternative to food sharing in our country, is of great importance in the future for more efficient use of food resources. The implementation of a food-sharing system can address the shortage and extravagance of food in Uzbekistan while promoting social cohesion and sustainability. The challenges of implementing the system are significant, in addition to this the government and other stakeholders can work together to establish a legal framework, invest in infrastructure, and raise awareness among the population to ensure the success of the system.

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